

GOOD GOVERNANCE: ROLE OF PUBLIC SERVANTS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT: *Governance has become so vast and complex that the government of the people, for the people and by the people has become the government of the people, by the government and for the people. The logic behind the idea of governance supports the development of political and administrative structures that offer the potentials for political stability and national development. Public servant in this regard plays significant role for the successful achievement of good governance. This study is expected to explain the relationship between politicians, public servants and good governance while it further revealed the efficiency of the application of the law in force, the efficacy of the decisions made by government, and the political responsibility and accountability of elected officials in relation to the demand expressed by civil society. The study is qualitative in nature, as it based its theoretical framework on structural functionalism. It submits that there is need for full respect for citizen's rights as the public service is a major change agent in Nigeria's quest for enhanced progress, hence the on-going reformation of the Nigerian public service is in line to achieve the purpose of good governance and deal with the challenges therein.*

KEYWORDS: *Good Governance, Public Servant, Political Office Holders, Relationship.*

INTRODUCTION

Government has become more ineffective because its' ability to secure compliance with its policies had diminished. This was partly because of the intractability of the problems facing government, and excessive citizens' expectations with regards to good governance. The culture

of political and administrative arbitrariness has been the major characteristic undermining good governance in Nigeria.

Governance is, therefore, the formal, specific, clearly identified activity, act or manner of governing. Governments do not act as neutral arbiters instead they exercise agenda which carries along the public service of a state, as various governmental institutions and structures are developed. The existence of these institutions implies that the government also develops rules, expectations, values, and ethics on the basis of which it carries on its activities. Therefore, the government acting on behalf of the state, can take the life of a human being, through legal execution; the government can take the money of a human being through taxation; the government can even remove the individual's right to vote or be voted for by law. In this respect, it is possible to talk of political or democratic governance, economic governance, corporate governance, environmental governance, amongst others. One thing which is evident irrespective of the functioning or non-functioning of the system is the existence of a symbiotic relationship between government and the governed.

The nature of civil servant relationship changes not only with respect to a particular policy sector, but also over time and due to changes in the dominant political ideology of the time, or changes in political leadership, its characteristics, texture and operating principles and procedures. It was in support of this assertion that Jomoh (2004) quoted Max Weber in his work that "all operations in a bureaucratic system are carried out through the instrumentality of procedures, rules and regulations". Thus, the effectiveness of government is to a large extent, determined by the efficiency and competence of the civil service, as the civil service is not a political body whose members serve in the different branches of government.

A good civil servant is a *sine qua non* for speedy and effective execution of government policies, if Nigeria is to catch up with the developed nations of the world. This was why Onasanya (1999) asserted that the establishment of an overall policy on personnel matters has the advantage of obliging top management to think through its ultimate goals and set the character of its actions in the pursuit of these goals. Meanwhile Nigerians always praise the government for coming out with good policies, but are quick to point out that the problem lies always at the point of implementation, thereby indicting the civil servants. Morlino (2002) quoted O'Donnell as saying that a closer look at the concrete problems of implementation should be accompanied by an awareness of some opposing forces that have received attention in numerous papers and studies. This attention was as a result of the first rigorous application of laws, or, in certain cases, the relationship with an only superficially efficient bureaucracy that could have particular negative consequences for the most socially weak and vulnerable members of the society; while it is possible to use the law as a genuine 'political weapon'. Okoh (2005) pointed out that in the Nigerian work environment and organizations, many workers are dissatisfied and frustrated while a few in the minority are satisfied. If Okoh's assertions were to be true, it therefore means

that negligence, disobedience and incompetence on the part of some Nigerian's civil servants, could hamper proper implementation of governmental policies that promotes good governance.

Succinctly, one of the foremost responsibilities of the public service is the attainment of good governance as it affects the welfare of citizens and also accounts for the pace of socio-economic development of the country. Given Nigeria's huge endowment in resources, with self-less and vision driven political leaders, after decades of independence, Nigeria should be one of the most highly developed African countries. The development and application of procedures, rules and regulations are used to obtain clarity in the operating processes in a bureaucratic system. However, mismanagement of the nation's resources has made it difficult for Nigerian public administrators to maximize these advantages and use it to attain the desired height of good and purposeful governance. The State has a legitimate and positive role to promote the welfare of the people. Therefore, the will of the people practically meant the will of the most numerous and the most active part of the people, i.e., the majority.

On the other hand, to properly address some of the salient issues hindering the effectiveness of good governance and the role of public servants in nation building, the objectives of this paper is to deal with the following: determine the role of public servants in the attainment of good governance in Nigeria; examine the quality of leadership in the attainment of good governance; to ascertain if corruption, venality and other vices had been inimical to the implementation of governmental policies that promote good governance; and to ascertain if cordial relationship exist between political office holders and public servants in Nigeria. The study based its analysis and findings on scholarly materials, books, articles in journals including periodicals and the internet. It took cognizance of some major contributors to good governance and the role of public servants and its effectiveness in nation building.

Notwithstanding, the role of public servant in Nigeria evolved as the bedrock of the executive arm of government. Its' main task came to be the implementation and execution of the policies decided on by the legislature or those appointed by the legislature to carry on the executive work of government. However, policy measures and implementation, often, failed to achieve the desired results when there are, strong opposition from the public servants thereby inhibiting the attainment of good governance and sustainable growth and development. With regards to these, the study is to ascertain why public servants have not been on the part of sustainable development to achieve the much desired growth that accrues from good and purpose driven governance.

FRAMEWORK OF ANALYSIS

The framework of analysis for this study, took its form from the structural functionalism theory. The structural functionalism theory was developed from the work of a social anthropologist,

A. R. Radcliff-Brown (1881-1955), and systematically formulated by the American sociologist, Talcott Parsons (1902-1979). Structural functionalism seeks out the 'structural' aspects of the social system under consideration (the public service), and then studies the processes which function to maintain social structures. In this context, structure primarily refers to normative patterns of behaviour (regularized patterns of action in accordance with norms), while function explains how such patterns operate as systems. A "system" refers to an organized whole with interdependent parts, regular patterns of interaction, known boundaries, structures, and functions performed by structures. What this means is that a political system refers to security organizations which help maintain domestic order in a society.

Structural-functionalism in this study sees society and the civil service as built upon order, interrelation, and balance amongst the various parts as a means of maintaining the smooth functioning of the whole in order to achieve good and purposeful governance. It further viewed shared norms and values as the basis of society, focuses on social order based on tacit agreements between groups, organizations, institutions, and views social change as occurring in a slow and orderly fashion. Structural functionalism has been generally agreed on to be an offshoot of the general systems theories. It is simply a means of explaining what political structures perform, what basic functions in the political system and under what conditions in any given system. This approach therefore assumes that a political system is composed of several structures with specific objective functions to perform, a process for its attainment and the effect of its performance. According to Cammack (1998), in order for a political system to run smoothly and enjoy a healthy autonomy or boundary maintenance between polity and society, there must be a way to avoid any rush of unprocessed claims or demands without direction or control by the political system. Citizen demands must be selected, channeled, and controlled. Any "rush" or "eruption" of diverse claims by the citizenry is to be avoided; otherwise the political system will become overwhelmed by direct societal pressures.

Good governance is only achievable if the social structure functions effectively for the generality of the society. Therefore civil servants must endeavour to maintain a good working relationship with those that have been elected politically to hold public office, notwithstanding their political affiliation and ethnic relations. This would help build a social structure that is acceptable to all. As an ideal political system utilizes un-fragmented and differentiated structures for interest articulation, and the political parties, for example, are not overly politicized nor tied to particular ideologies or interests. According to Robert Merton he postulates that the function of a particular social structure contributes to make the social system functional and that the maintenance and survival of the system are contingent on the functional interdependence of the diverse structures within the whole system [Merton, 1957].

Good Governance and its Role in Societal Development

Good governance is a system of governance that is able to unambiguously identify the basic values of the society where values are economic, political and socio-cultural issues including human rights, and pursue these values through an accountable and honest administration (Chopra, 1997). While Andre (2007) quoted Hinden (1963) in his 1989 report on the prospects for development in Sub-Saharan Africa and the World Bank, as he defined governance “as the exercise of political power to manage the nations’ affairs”.

The practice of good governance therefore, is ideally based on, and guided by the existence of a sound democratic constitution that enables the government to manage the affairs of the state effectively while empowering the citizenry to participate in governance and hold the government accountable. This accounts for why Zimako (2009) posits that responsible government all over the world place utmost priority on the welfare of citizens and are accountable for the pace of socio-economic development. While Imhanlahimhin (2000) in citing M.P Todaro asserted that “development must be conceived of as a multi-dimensional process involving major changes in social structures, popular attitudes, and national institutions, as well as acceleration of economic growth, the reduction of inequality and the eradication of absolute poverty”. Accordingly the study observed that these would lead to a peaceful, equitable, harmonious and just society where every citizen has a strong sense of national identity and belonging, which is truly valued by the society, as the citizens are motivated adequately and empowered to contribute to nation building to meet the yearnings and aspiration of Nigerian’s vision 20:2020. This vision was described by Oaikhena and Osawe (2012) as a call for all Nigerians, regardless of ethnicity, economic status, or religion to unite and stand behind a common cause of placing the country firmly on a path of sustainable growth, and taking it to its rightful place in the comity of nations leading to the development of the society. Societal development makes life more meaningful in all its ramifications and entirety which includes economic, legal, political, administrative, social, cultural, regions and personal aspects and the establishment of functional order.

As a result, detail structures and processes must be available through which the functional requirements are met in a society. This was why Leon (1979) asserted that “a society will make the most progress when each individual in that society is stimulated to make the greatest effort for himself or herself personally”, while there is adequate commitment to public good through the charismatic and sterling quantities of the leadership. Leadership, whether it is political or general, presupposes the ideals of altruism (Bayo, 2005).

Leadership Quality in the Attainment of Good Governance

Leaders have been adjudged as men and women who have not lost their sense of reasoning, as they feel obliged by moral law to refrain from evil and to do good. Surely, all men have the experience of this obligation to refrain from evil and to do good. This good brings about good leadership qualities that promotes good relationship amongst the populace and enhance the

quality of life of the people. Quality represents uniqueness, responsibility and tolerance. It is with regard to this that the study postulates that, it is the responsibility of leaders to discipline those under them, or that a high office entails a heavy responsibility. Meanwhile, current debates rest on the conclusion that Nigerian leadership suffers from extreme moral depravity and attitudinal debauchery.

Leaders must be men and women who take their duties, obligations, promises, seriously and does everything possible to fulfill them promptly and efficiently. All these involve sacrifice, as one of the qualities that are essential for good and effective leadership is discipline. Self-discipline in leaders, leads to the attainment of good governance. Thus as Zimako (2009) quoted Kolawole “if Nigeria is to attain its foreign policy goals such as provision of effective leadership, guaranteeing peace and security in the region and lastly, the need to enhance the economic potentials and development of the Nigerian nation, there must always be a readiness for some sacrifice both in human and material resources”.

Leadership is a dynamic process at work in a group whereby one individual over a particular period of time, and in a particular organisational context, influences the other group members to commit themselves freely to the achievement of group tasks or goals. This was why Oaikhena (2011) asserted that the existence of a leader in any establishment is to effectively control, direct and guide subordinates towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. As a result leadership is vision driven, which portends good and visionary governance.

Good governance therefore, provides a formidable platform for the people to exercise their rights in a liberal democracy. Liberalism advocates for individual freedom as its goal is to allow for individual development and societal growth at large. In order words periodical review of policies must be encouraged in order to guide the principles of objectivity as the review will bring about progress, performance and direction of governance through the various policy formulation and subsequent implementation. Onansanya (1999) in quoting Calson Dick, posited that “policy is a guide for making administrative decisions and an established way of doing business and directing actions in specified areas of management” while policy implementation is the stage of policy-making between the establishment of a policy and the consequences of the policy for the people whom it affects. The public service appears to be an impoverished concept of management which overemphasizes routine control and neglects other dimensions such as managing change and managing relationships within the establishment. Such relationship has created a wide gap between the civil servant and the political office holders to attain good governance.

Adebayo (2008) revealed that the civil service possesses the machinery, the repository of knowledge stored in files and in their memory, the institutional discipline and hierarchical

command to formulate and tender advice on various options and alternatives of policies open to the government. This means that the civil servants will outline the various options, examine each one for advantages and disadvantages in terms of cost, time factor and political acceptability.

As a result leaders are expected to purge themselves of corrupt tendencies that could negate good policy implementation and the actualization of good governance as the challenges of the Nigeria-state remains a daunting one. There should be zero tolerance to corruption and the need to promote respect for rules and regulations in the country, if we are to attain the much desired good governance.

Hindrance to Policy Implementation and Good Governance

Policies are programmes the government has set aside to address teething issues in the society. In fact, the active participation of a broad spectrum of Nigerians in various ministries, agencies, state and local governments, representatives from the private sector, as well as development consultants and non-governmental organizations are geared towards the development of workable policies for the country. It was to support this assertion that Ikelegbe (2006) conceptualize policies as that which has to do with particular needs and problems which are responses to challenges arising from an environment, as it provides the framework within which present and future actions are undertaken. It is the nation's policy to conduct all her business in an honest and ethical manner, thereby encouraging a zero-tolerance approach to, bribery and corruption, and being committed to acting professionally, fairly and with integrity in all relationships and business dealings. It will then become counter-productive if policies and programmes are not implemented to meet the yearning of the people. It was in views like these that Anwar (2011) quoted Leftwich, (1993) when he said that "good governance means an efficient, open, accountable and audited public service which has the bureaucratic competence to help design and implement appropriate public policies and at the same time an independent judicial system to uphold the law". Given Nigerian's history of wide income disparity, which has manifested in large-scale poverty, unemployment and poor access to healthcare, the nation's approach to policies and programmes have been a top-down approach, with government developing programs for the people rather than programmes designed, implemented, monitored and evaluated by the people themselves, thereby hampering transparency and accountability in budget implementation.

As a result since the people are not carried along in the development of policy formulation and subsequent implementation, there would evolve hindrance and manipulations of the policies which would have been geared for the betterment of the people. All over the world people expect performance from elected politicians in terms of development. As development is tied to good governance and effective and efficient policy implementation, that is expected to be participatory

and concerned with the respect to rule of law. Furtherance to this development, few instances are hereby cited, these are:-

i. Lack of Social Relations: As Radcliff Brown puts it, individual human beings are the essential units of analysis and are connected by networks of social relation into an integrated whole. In view of these, major problems arise from the implementation of policies which could have resulted to good governance in Nigeria. Some of these problems are: bad leadership; political instability and lack of commitment on the part of politicians and civil servants; non-accountability and heavy politicization of all government institutions including the Judiciary; the existence of deep rooted corruption in the public service; bureaucratic structure; and, nepotism, whereby the rulers give privilege and unfair advantage to their family members, on public resources, which leads to the deprivation of the masses from opportunities, thereby paving the way for indiscipline. This could be the reason why Omoregbe (2008) said that, indiscipline is everywhere in the society; in the presidency, in the banks, in the post offices, in the ministries, in attitude to work, in the taste for expensive items – expensive cars, expensive cloths, expensive electronics, etc. He added that indiscipline is one of the major obstacles to development in any country, for unless the members of a society are disciplined how can they make things work? If this variable is allowed to continue there would be no progress in any society, as devotion to duty, honesty and efficiency would yield to self-interest and the craving for self-enrichment, as noticed in the Nigerian state. These negate the important characteristics of the civil service as it is supposed to be unreservedly neutral and impartial in economic and political issues for the attainment of good governance.

ii. Wrong Attitude: Wrong attitude to economic and political issues is a reflection of the society's wrong attitude to wealth and the manner of its acquisition. This wrong attitude further explains the increase in various forms of corruption such as embezzlement, inflation of contracts, bribery, ghost workers, conversion of government property to private use, etc. As a result, policy implementation in developing nations has become a disaster (Makinde, 2005).

iii. Corruption Resulting in Bad Leadership: Corruption has built a formidable platform in Nigerian's democracy as the Government appears to have embarked on a sincere commitment to eradicate corruption and other social vices in public service and in the larger society. The promotion of policies for the betterment of societies has been advanced by so many authors in explaining the ingredients of good governance. Good governance would not be achieved in Nigeria if we continue to celebrate, corruption and bad leadership. Corruption has become a national issue causing harm to the people and government almost everywhere in the country. Nigerians must understand the genesis of Nigerian's image problem and should put the blame for Nigeria's sordid image where it belongs. Nigerians are not stigmatized because of their citizenship, but because Nigerian seems to have bad image, caused mostly by bad leadership. The corrupt individuals who parade themselves as leaders contribute immensely to the sordid image of the nation and the insults on Nigerians abroad. No step to fight corruption will be effective unless all forms of corruption – political, economic, moral and administrative are

fought with a sense of commitment and will. These assertions, if taken into consideration in the discharge of duties, would address some of the major hindrances negating good governance and policy implementation in the country. As Merton (1957) puts it “there should be detailed account of structure and functional arrangement so as to achieve a condition in which all parts of the social system work in harmony in order to achieve a common goal of system maintenance and survival.

Additionally, Kaufmann and Kraay (2007) gave some indices on how good governance should be assessed; these are (a) voice and accountability, (b) political stability (c) government effectiveness, (d) regulatory quality (e) rule of law, and (f) control of corruption. These six dimensions covered the political, economic and, institutional aspects of governance, as they are normative and have high association with democracy and economic development. These indices would stand as a challenge to what could hinder a successful implementation of policies leading to good governance and cordial relationship in the public service.

Promoting Cordial Relationship between Political Office Holders and Public Servants

A healthy relationship is required between the civil servants and the political class. It is, indeed, crucial to a democratic governance. The relationship between the politicians and bureaucrats over the years has gone through different phases and there have been several significant reforms to enhance this relationship. According to Omoregbe (2008) “...everybody is important in the society and every profession is important, as a result members of the society have a sense of duty to ensure that things move smoothly in the society as life will be made easier and more comfortable for people”, hence effective mechanisms must be available for social control purposes within a system.

Succinctly, it has been established universally that good governance begins with the establishment of quality relationship between the political and bureaucratic leaders. As stated by Richard Rose, quoted by Leon (1979) ‘the metaphorical ship of state has one tiller but two pairs of hands that give it direction, one belonging to party politicians in elective positions or appointed political leaders and the other to higher civil servants, led by Permanent Secretaries. To this end, it is vital for the civil servants and the politicians to maintain cordial relationship to enable them continue to render services to the people, for the effectuation and sustenance of the social contract that binds the governed and the governors together. One thing which is evident irrespective of the functioning or non-functioning of a system is the existence of a symbiotic relationship between government and the governed (Bolaji, 2007). In relation to this, the combined efforts of both parties is a compelling force for progress as exemplified in the first republic when the political masters and the bureaucratic leaders worked collaboratively to record the milestones in the West, East, North and later Mid-West Regions of the country. This era has often been mentioned as the golden era in Nigerian’s history.

However, by way of complementing and encouraging cordial relationship between the public office holders and the civil servants, this study brought to the fore ways to this improvement, that is; (i) devising good strategy to manage relationship rather than living it to chance or adopting the *I-Don't Care* attitude; (ii) harmonious relationship between ministers and their aides in policy making as a strategic imperative for strengthening and enriching the public service with knowledge and competencies from other sources. This is with regards to the need to harness the intellectual capacities and professional depth of highly qualified aides in the delivery of government's policies and programmes; (iii) encouraging wider participation in governance; (iv) recognizing the need for senior civil servants and indeed the body of higher civil servants to align themselves totally with the agenda of their ministers/ministries and other political leaders in order to give effect to the President's priorities as reflected in ministerial responsibilities; (v) appreciating the need for highly qualified civil servants to earn the respect of their ministers by: *demonstrating administrative competence; speaking the truth; deploying the best talents to handle emerging core concerns; avoiding negative gossips; and avoiding negative opinions and perceptions which may tend to damaging of system*. If these are taken into consideration, the quest for good governance in terms of nation building and policy implementation would be achieved without much ado. These could therefore be the reason why Merton (1957) wrote that "functions are performed as long as it meets the satisfactions of the various individuals or groups affected in a political system". More so venality and social vices that could have affected the smooth attainment of good governance would be eliminated. The elimination of social vices is the responsibility of civil servants who have either by appointment or employment had pledged loyalty to serve the nation with diligence, commitment and ethics. Public service ethics are broad norms that stipulate how public servants should behave and exercise judgment and discretion in carrying out their official duties (Tunde & Omobolaji, 2009).

Social Vices Against Policy Implementation and Good Governance

Social vices, like corruption have had their consequences on the actualization of good and purposeful governance in Nigeria. Corruption is the major bane of sustainable development and public programme implementation in Nigeria, as it consists of depravity, venality or speculation in playing social role. Toyo (2006) agreed that corrupt acts normally involves some kind of cover up or diversionary conduct such as falsification, hypocrisy, tyranny, or violence to men or property. It is obvious that corruption of public office has existed in Nigeria since the establishment of modern structures of public administration in the country by British Colonial Administration (Iroanusi, 2006). However its escalation has coincided with the expansion of administrative structures and the full development of the public sector.

The colonial civil servants were before now, said to be men and women of high sense of mission, dedication, discipline and motivation who were prepared to make sacrifices. Their

course was to achieve the goals of imperial policy and they did what they were expected to do with the highest sense of dedication, enterprise, initiative and even risk.

Although, the civil service remains a vital mechanism for rapid socio-economic development of developing countries like Nigeria, over the years, the government occupies a significant position as a dominant instrument of change. Right from the beginning, one needs to realize that the civil service is a key instrument to the survival of any governmental setting and indeed national development. In a general sense, the civil service provides the semblance of government. Thus, the effectiveness and productivity of any government is largely determined by the efficiency of the civil service. As the administrative and technical support to the governing apparatus, the civil service remains the only viable mechanism for policy initiation or formulation, policy advice and policy implementation. The civil service must therefore be encouraged to imbibe the spirit of discipline and respect for constituted authority and shorn vices that could damage the image of the country. Vices like corruption. As corruption contributes immensely to inhibition of economic performance; affects investment and economic growth, and it is antithetical to national development. This could be the reason why Salu and Aremu, (2004) said that in Nigeria, corruption led to decaying infrastructure, inadequate medical services, falling educational standards, mismanagement of foreign loans, bloated imported bills and public expenditure, reduces production capacity, distortion of the economy through waste and misallocation.

Role of Public Servants in Nation Building

The post-independence period in the 1960s in Nigeria witnessed an enormous expansion, of government intervention in national economies when the public sector was seen as a major contributor to economic growth and socio-political stability. Thus the civil servants inherited from the colonial rulers in the 1960s the Weberian bureaucratic model (Ademolekun 2002), which provides relevant data for understanding the challenges that, new ideas have to be overcome to truly become innovations and best practices. This justified the role of public servants in the intervention of the nations' development, inherited from the colonial masters. Public servants were then seen as enabling the state to carry out activities that private entrepreneur could not perform and also to reduce the dominance of foreign investment. In other words, there was need to understand the function, structure, orientation and organizational culture as well as challenges facing public servants in nation building and the quest for good governance. Public servants have basically evolved in developed countries with stable democratic political systems and competitive markets, the application of the concept of good governance to developing countries that are at different development stages may have unintended and serious consequences for the citizens especially the poor. Developing countries are being asked to do everything which works in developed countries and consequently the good governance agenda in the developing world has grown long over the years. Recognizing

this problem, Grindle (2004) has recently argued for *good enough* governance, for poverty reduction and reform in developing countries, that the concept of 'good enough governance', though still in its infancy, represents a strong case for contextualizing or indigenizing the notion of good governance in the developing world to set realistic and achievable reform objectives for each country.

In Nigeria the civil service structures which were based on the bureaucratic model led to inefficient organizations, excessive red tape and structural arrangements that impeded as much or more than serve the implementation of public policy to a formidable outcome. Policy outcomes were intended or unintended consequences of policies that flow from action or inaction by government. Analysts of public administration have always pointed out that for any policy to redistribute existing resources away from privileged groups, it is bound to attract more bureaucratic and social oppositions (Lowi 1964; Thomas & Grindle 1990). Thus, policy is adopted, adapted and drifts, morphs and mutates through the implementation process. The extent of drift and mutation depends on a myriad of variables, only some of which can be controlled by policy makers (Oaikhena & Osawe, 2012). It is in line with this also, that the Nigerian vision 20:2020 mission statement proposed that by 2020, Nigeria will have large, strong, diversified, sustainable and competitive economy that would effectively harness the talents and energies of its people and responsibly exploits its natural endowments to guarantee a high standard of living of life to its citizens (NV.20.2020). The citizens constitute the major resources in themselves or through their exploitation of the physical environment, which pay for policy activity and implementation (Ikelegbe 2006), thereby promoting the effort of the public servants in nation building.

Basically, the role public servants must play should be in the area of collective effort towards equation and morale productivity. This means that civil servants should develop a conscious attitude, realizing the existence of principles related to the matter at hand; developing a responsible attitude, deciding which will be adopted and acted upon; and developing an experimental attitude, and experimenting and watching results. By so doing optimum capacity will be achieved in the establishment as these would go a long way in ensuring that sufficient, motivated and competent workforce remains in the civil service to help take the service to the next level of capacity building and development of the society.

Succinctly, the role of building a society presupposes the following functions and behavioural traits of the civil servants, these are, (a) adequate measures should be put in place for policy implementation; (b) achievement oriented behavior should be encouraged; (c) judicious use of authority is necessary; (d) pursuit of happiness for the people should be paramount; (e) use of reason and experience as the basis of decisions is a criteria; (f) uprightness, friendliness and firmness of devotion in dealing with others; (g) improving bureaucratic functions by way of simplification of rules, regulations and procedures of work; (h) civil servants should be open

and transparent in their working environment (i) civil servants should be instruments for a responsive and accountable administration; (j) mobilizing the society to support the system of rule of law; (k) putting an end to the system of patronage and nepotism from government organizations; (l) civil servants should focus on economic, social and political development; and (m) civil servants should work within a value system that determines the conduct of their actions. Values, that consists of opinion of colleagues and cultural values of the society.

In other words, the populace would be rest assured that good governance will not be a mirage but attainable and sustainable. The study noted that, modest beginning towards developing a full scale public service for good governance, and indeed specific models will enable the people recognize and realize their goals and objectives towards nation building, hence it is a collective effort. Thus the greatest waste in any establishment is the failure to recognize and use the abilities of people, and to recognize that it is people who produce the strategy, structure, and systems of the establishment (Oaikhena *et al*, 2013).

SUMMARY/CONCLUSION

The existence of formal patterns of administering the people in terms of the provision of good governance and the willingness to cooperate with the citizens cannot be overemphasized as clearly revealed by the theory relating to structural functionalism in this paper. The study also revealed that little attention has been paid to one of the most critical relationships in democratic governance, that is, the relationship between civil servants and political office holders, as they succinctly failed to promote professionalism in the discharge of their duties. This lack of synergy the study observed, had led to slow development, lack of integrity and accountability. As noted too, accountability of the governors to the governed increases transparency, openness and citizen participation in governance. To a certain extent therefore, there is a neat distinction of the original public administration thinkers, whereby politicians make policy, civil servants implement policy, and the issues are often time, always more theoretical than real. Good governance starts with a quality relationship between the permanent government and political leaders. In order words for good governance to be achieved and developed through the various machinery of implementation of governmental policies, there must be a synergy between political office holders and the civil servants. The role of public servants in this regard is therefore to work for the common objectives of ensuring interdependence and good inter personnel relationship with those in the domain of governance. In relations to these the civil servants in Nigeria must ensure that what has been gained through Nigerian's Independence since 1960, in terms of economic growth, technology and human development, must be sustained.

As highlighted in this study, good governance is not only for a type of government and its related political values but also for certain kinds of additional components. It implies that government is democratically organized within a democratic political culture and with efficient

administrative organizations, plus the right policies, particularly in the economic sphere. Thus civil servants should be appointed to permanent post where hierarchy of central administration is established.

In a nutshell public office holders charged with the responsibility of using public resources to obtain results for the good of the public must meet public policy objectives in terms of socio-economic development. Bureaucracy may be slow in its response to development in national life and may appear to be resistant to change, but this must not be portrayed wholly in bad light. The peculiarity of bureaucracy does not allow reformers, revolutionaries and tyrants to trample upon the rights and ways of life of the people with ease and impunity. The core challenge lies in developing a governance model that fits the nation's current economic and political conditions, and this challenge should be tackled head long by political office holders and the civil servants in a combined effort.

However, modern government has had a way of eroding whatever truth there was to this distinction, hence there is a breakdown in trust and cooperation between those who occupy the permanent government (civil servants) and their political masters. The civil servants feel that their advice is not heeded while the politicians feel that the permanent government undermines them with poor performance and with disloyalty. The paper concludes that there is a need for bureaucratic mechanism to continue to play the indispensable role of stabilizing and preserving government and civilization, as this would reduce disenchantment and sluggishness in bureaucracy, and offer a comforting dependability of a formalized structure built on a constitutional and statutory foundation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based the prevailing body of knowledge on the subject matter and the findings made, the researchers recommended the following:

- Cordial relationship should be promoted between political office holders and the civil servants. This is necessary, if democratic dividends will be attained in a democratic dispensation, as it would further lead to even development, promote policy implementation and adequate monitoring.
- Elected leaders should seek to understand and respond to the perceptions and positions of the citizens through the civil servants.
- Public officers should not put themselves in a position where their personal interest conflicts with their duties.
- The reformation effort of the federal government towards the enhancement and proficiency of the civil service should be sustained.
- It is a known fact that there is no substitute to civil service as an instrument of implementation of governmental policies and programmes. Therefore, the civil servants

must revert and maintain their roles of unobtrusive advisers and faithful implementers of government decisions, policies and programmes and become real obedient servant of the people.

- The best way out for all those holding positions of public trust lies in the path of probity. They should not only uphold the laws of the country and live within their legitimate income but should be seen to do so.
- Officers who hold public office should be made to declare their assets before they are sworn into office and at the expiration of such tenure, defaulters should be made to face the law. This has been emphasized by many scholars.
- There should be an enabling platform where relationship issues between political office holders and civil servants are discussed, this would help to iron out salient issues that could negate a smooth relationship.
- All inclusive style of governance should be encouraged between the political office holders and the civil servants.
- Other recommendations include the promotion of professionalism in the civil service; ethical reorientation and attitudinal change; effective career management and workforce training; building and fast tracking the internal and external processes for concrete outcomes; and ensuring that civil servants imbibe and actualize the spirit of dignity of labour at all levels towards enhancing productivity.

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